
THE CONCEPT OF SPIRITUALITY IN THE ACTIVITY OF THE SOCIAL WORKER DOLLARITY

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Abstract.

The article covers the tables of the predominance and relevance of the spiritual aspect in the professional activities of social work in the period of sustainable development in our country today.

Keywords.

social worker, spiritual maturity, society, Confucius, virtue, activity, ethics.

Introduction

The demand for social workers in general in this field has already developed, however, special training of specialists in this field took place in Western Europe in the 19th and 20th centuries had begun to develop. One of the main reasons for this is in the life of society the high level of socialization and the need for a social worker is the origin. The first teacher in life for a person is need and experience. Exactly these bring a person to the level of distinguishing between useful and harmful things. In society when the need for certain things increases, the supply for it appears. Social work helps people solve relationships between people and aimed at helping social changes in society, their vital to provide assistance and support in order to improve their well-being is a professional activity.

Social as a profession that works with all layers of society It is important that the moral aspects of the employee are sufficiently polished earns. People at different levels, especially social work, are spiritual in their professional activities views about the role of the factor have been of interest to thinkers since time immemorial. In particular, Confucius puts spiritual virtue above all else in man and society and associates it mainly with moral categories. Spiritual, domestic, spiritual to people taking into account the fact that the social worker will help must acquire all the spiritual skills at the level of professional activity.

Literature Analysis And Methodology

He contributed to the development of social work in the coverage of the article In the works of European and Uzbek scientists and the wisdom of philosophers

words were used. In particular, "Social work" created under the leadership of Ganiyeva M. "Ethics" book was widely used.

In the process of analyzing the topic, several local and foreign scientists studies and research such as observation and generalization in the coverage of the topic methods were used.

Results

The great thinker Aristotle - "Man's spiritual qualities, on the one hand, are whole in activities that bring benefit and pleasure to the society, on the other hand, to the person himself is formed," he rightly emphasizes.

Since ancient times, scientists have been concerned with the issue of education in the improvement of human spiritual qualities special attention. At the same time, a number of researchers spiritual criteria generally defined as follows:

1. Free, independent thinking;
2. Taking into account the opinion of others;
3. To be knowledgeable, willing, moral, public-spirited, loyal to the country;
4. To love one's profession;
5. Incident - reacting to incidents;
6. Active participation in community work

Thus, they have a leading place in the formation of social workers the main regulator of activity and behavior and to social and social workers belongs to the component of ethics, which represents the ideological elevation and faith.

Spiritual maturity of social workers is not only in certain conditions It is also formed by important conclusions during life experience and its society position can be measured by this.

"Social Work Ethics: Principles and Theory" in Colombo in 1994 document named was accepted. This document consists of two parts

- I. "International Declaration of Principles of Social Work"
- II. "International Ethical Standards for Social Workers" is composed of parts.

In the dererization of ethical principles of social work, the following principles illuminated:

1. Each person is a unique phenomenon, which should be taken into account from a moral point of view.
2. Everyone harms the rights of others in meeting their needs has the right to act without delivery and it is his own to increase the welfare of society should contribute.

3. Each society, regardless of the form of government, each of its members to the maximum should strive to provide with treats as much as possible.

4. Social workers are subject to the principles of social justice.

5. Social workers share their knowledge, skills and abilities with individual people, for the development of groups, communities and societies, to resolve personal-social conflicts should be spent to eliminate their consequences.

6. Social work is based on rejection of discrimination. so it is the gender of the customers, regardless of age, nationality, religion, language, political beliefs, sexual orientation look is done.

7. Social workers protect the rights of every person and social group, their independence and while respecting the dignity of the UN Charter of Human Rights and other international based on documents.

8. Social work is based on the principle of protecting the privacy of clients freedom of choice and professional secrecy, the client's own rights and the essence of "personal work" including the right to be explained.

9. Social workers maintain professional confidentiality, even if it is against our current legislation even though Social work is based on client participation and cooperation. Social employees and customers in solving any complex task they encounter should cooperate with Social work as a professional activity on human qualities On the one hand, it affects, on the other hand, it is specific to the owners of each profession it is necessary to take into account the presence of qualities.

Spiritual qualities are directly related to the moral norm, and human behavior - evaluates and sees certain aspects of the character in a generalized form. He determines whether he should act. therefore, the moral of the social worker qualities - not only his human qualities, but also his professional activities depends. Spiritual qualities are the manifestation of the spiritual factor at the individual level knowledge, ethics, education, art and aesthetics to social workers It allows for valuable appropriation and reuse.

In order to increase the efficiency of social work in neighborhoods and it is necessary to restore the staff of "Social work" in pre-school education institutions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the issue of spirituality is important for every society It is a calculated issue. In his time, the great scholar Abu Nasr Farabi said, "Virtuous people city" contains 12 qualities in the formation of young people as leaders emphasized the need to be united. All 12 traits in one person It is impossible to summarize, because people with such innate qualities are very rare and they are

rare people. if it is not found, even if six or five of the above qualities are perfected, he is He can lead the city of virtues because of his intelligence and intelligence. That's why as a social worker meant to work with different layers of society First of all, he should be able to act as a mirror for the society. He is his own profession in the course of his work, he strives to acquire and promote spiritual qualities necessary. High moral qualities in the professional activity of social workers is the most important factor to achieve success. In turn, if social work if the employee shows his spiritual qualities in the team, he has reputation and attention social workers who are the environment as an element of the whole society becomes an example of spiritual maturity.

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